

A Review of Feature Extraction and Classification Methods for MODI Lipi Recognition

Lekha Gadpade¹, Aruna Chamatkar²

Department of Electronics and Computer Science, R.T.M.N.U., Nagpur, Maharashtra, India¹

Computer Science and MCA Department, Kamla Nehru Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India²

Lekha.thawkar@gmail.com¹, aruna.ayush1007@gmail.com²

Abstract: Government of Maharashtra primarily used MODI Lipi from the 17th century onwards for administrative work. The use of this script slowly phased out in the 1950's because of the difficulty in making printing blocks due to its cursive style. The Government of Maharashtra has recently shown interest in the documentation and preservation of the script. The hurdle that is being faced is the automatic recognition of the script because of its irregular and flowing structure. This paper reviews the major techniques that have been used for recognizing the characters of MODI Lipi. It covers both the traditional feature based methods as well as the contemporary deep learning approaches. Techniques such Zernike moments, wavelet based analysis, chain-code and junction features skew correction, etc. have been explored by researchers earlier. Comparative studies of these methods have shown that hybrid approaches, particularly CNN models combined with classifiers, like SVM tend to give higher accuracy. This study outlines the progress made so far to highlighting the research directions and the potential to improve the performance of the MODI OCR systems.

Keywords: Pattern Recognition, Feature Extraction, DCNN, MODI Lipi.

1. Introduction

The primary script used for Marathi from the 17th century up to the early 20th century was MODI Lipi. Its popularity among clerks, traders, accountants as well as government officials was because of its flowing curves and continuous strokes made rapid script has 46 basic characters, 36 consonants and 10 vowels.

The recognition of the characters in MODI script is complicated as many of the characters for look visually similar and moreover their shapes shift depending on the presence of vowel signs as conjunct consonants. The name 'MODI' is derived from the Marathi verb 'Modane' which translates as 'to use as break'. This reflects the unique style of writing the script using cursive and rounded characters that enabled fast and continuous writing without lifting the pen too often. 'Boru' a bamboo pen was used traditionally for writing, thus to ensure smooth and uninterrupted strokes.

The evolution of MODI script is from the family of Nagari script along with some visual characteristics of Devanagari scripts. It differs from there two scripts in stroke, structure, direction, and, rendering conventions. And the absence of char word boundary markers.

2. Historical Background

The use MODI Lipi goes back to the 13th century. Thousands of legal documents, administrative registers as well as handwritten done records were originally in MODI in the state of "Maharashtra. Bharat Itihas Sanshodhan Mandal (BISM), Pune" has a manuscript that back to 1389 that the script was widely used during the eras of Maharaj and the Peshwas.

The origin and spread of MODI script has been interpreted differently by various scholars some attribute its spread to Hemadpanta, a prime minister and administrator in the 13th century Yadav kingdom, while other attribute it to the early Mauryan scripts. Irrespective of its origin, this scripts remained in use for almost nine hundred years as shown in table 1. It evolved over the different periods Yadava, Shiva Peshawa and Anglo, with changes being reflected in the height, curvature the angle of the character as shown in shown in figure 1.

The mid two entries witnessed the replacement of MODI with Devanagari for formal as well as everyday written work. Despite the decline MODI manuscripts are an essential part of Maharastra as historical records thus making it crucial to preserve and digitize them.

The use of machine learning techniques for character recognition of various languages and scripts has been researched upon by various scholars. This study aims to identify the approaches that are most relevant - MODI Lipi. Literature review of studies that applied a variety of Machine Learning Algorithms for character recognition tasks and compared their performances, datasets and methodology, was done.

The following research questions were framed based on the literature review done.

- a) What are the most popular machine learning techniques used in Character recognition?
- b) Which of these technique achieve the most accuracy?

What are the publicly accessible dataset of MODI Lipi Characters?

Table 1. Tabular representation of MODI Script during different periods.

<i>Period</i>	<i>Script Name</i>	<i>Description</i>
12th Century	Adyakalin	The earliest form of MODI Script
13th Century	Yadavkalin	Evolved version of MODI Script. Marking a new stage in its development
14th-16th Century	Bahamanikalin	The next phase of MODI Script development during the Bahamani dynasty period.
17th Century	Shivkalin	The MODI Script further developed under the influence Shivaji Era.
18th Century	Chitnis	The MODI Script used in official correspondence.
Lasted till 1818	Peshavekalin	Refined and standardized for extensive use in administration and trade
1818-1952	Anglakalin or British Era	The final stage of MODI Script under British rule, incorporating English influence.

Fig. 1: MODI Lipi Vowels and Consonants

Fig.2: A brief view of selection and characterization of research papers for Literature review

3. Literature Review

A number of studies exploring different approaches for recognition of MODI script as mention in figure 2, using both traditional machine language methods as well as modern deep learning architecture have been carried out by various researchers as described in table 2.

As Lekha G. and Aruna C. have been done a review on several traditional machine learning algorithms for MODI Lipi character recognition, with SVM Method showing superior accuracy and overall performance [1].

Several recognition techniques for character recognition were compared by Varpe and Sakhare, with the conclusion that convolutional Neural Network(CNN) gave the best accuracy among all the models that were evaluated by them[2].

Deep learning architectures, ResNet50 and Inception V3 were accessed by Chandankhede et. al. using a multi writer handwritten dataset. On preprocessing testing accuracy achieved by ResNet was 94.55% with a precision of 0.86 verses the accuracy of 93.923% with precision 0.843 given by Inception V3[3].

Hybrid as well as traditional feature based methods have also been examined by several researchers, Vowel recognition using Chain code Histograms and Intersection. Junction features for both MODI and Devanagari scripts

were studied by D.N. Besekar and Chandankhede et.al. They classified the data obtained using Bayesian Networks, KNN and SVM. Their came to the conclusion that specialized feature sets and larger databases were needed to recognize MODI vowels as there had shapes that closely resembled each other[32][34].

Zernike and Zernike Complex moments were studied by Kulkarni P.A. et.al. This study was carried out across six zoning patterns within 37 zones. The accuracies obtained were 94.9% and 94.78% respectively[4].

In a similar study Kulkarni S.A. compared Zernike moments with Hu's invariant and concluded that Zernike features were more reliable because of orthogonal and rotation invariants[11].

Besekar et.al. applied Zone based extraction for MODI numerals that were handwritten. The pixel values were converted into polar coordinates the accuracy obtained was 93.5% [6].

The method of seven invariant moments and Gaussian based clustering was worked on by Ajmire et.al. to recognize the handwritten Marathi vowels. The improvement seen in the accuracy was seen to rise to 62% from 59%[33].

Joseph et. al. used on-the-fly data augmentation and CNN architecture . the efficiency of the system was increased by these methods and achieved 99.78% accuracy[7].

Joseph et.al. used wavelet based techniques such as Daubechies, Haar, and Symlet wavelets along with a decision tree classifier on 4600 characters. Daubechies wavelet reported the highest accuracy of 91.75%[8].

Joseph and Colleagues used CNN model along with extensive data augmentation. They achieved an accuracy of 99.78% with on-the-fly augmentation and 99.47% with offline augmentation[9].

These authors further used the convolutional auto encoder based ,method for extracting features and achieved a accuracy of 99.4% with KNN and 99.3% accuracy with SVM[10].

Distance based technique used by them gave an accuracy of 99.28% using Eclidean distance verses 94% using Manhattan distance.[11]

Recent research on MODI OCR is shown to be dominated by Deep learning techniques. Tamhankar et.al training over 40000 samples across 31 classes and tested on 10000 samples to design a CNN with RELU activations and softmax output. They achieved an accuracy of 65%[12].

AlexNet was used by Mahajan et. al. on a dataset of around 58 characters that were handwritten with 100 samples of each to achieve an accuracy of 89.72%[13].

A DCCN and applied AlexNet was developed by Chandra et. al. for transfer learning. SVM was used to classify features that were extracted from multiple network layers, resulting in an accuracy of 92.32%[14].

Shah et. al. worked on the more specialized challengers of MODI OCR. The focus of their work was the absence of word boundaries and difficulty of segmentation of lines in the historical manuscripts. A feature map of size $V=(D \times H \times W)$ where H and W represent the height, and width after division by eight and D was the number of output channels (D=512). Was generated by their deep CNN model. A recognition accuracy of 99.97% was achieved by this method[15].

A dual threshold character segmentation method to address the continuous writing characteristics of the script was Professional MODI translation and localization services in order to preserve the ecosystem was also done by Translation services USA[18].

Additionally, studies exploring the challenges in document processing have also been done. In order to isolate the overlapping and touching characters, a background pixel density based segmentation method was proposed by Deshmukh et. al.[19].

They also proposed a robust line segmentation technique for handling overlapping text, multi skew characters and non uniform Shirorekha[19].

MODI image was enhanced by Slanki et. al. using an Ostu based threshold approach that was evaluated through PSNR and MSE metrics[20].

A feature recognition system that was hybrid was developed by Maurya et. al. This achieved an average

developed by Tamhankar et. al. This method gave a segmentation accuracy of 67%[16].

Efforts to map as well as preserve the scripts have also been done. To map MODI characters to the Devanagari script a CNN based framework was proposed by Sawant et. al. A dataset of 57 characters was used in this method[17].

CDAC pune developed digital tools such as web browser plugin and also an Android application in order to facilitate learning, digitization and long term preservation of the historical MODI manuscripts. An updated digital type face to analyzing the differences in the rendering patterns of MODI and Devanagari was designed by Chatterjee et. al.[18]

accuracy of 91.20% and a maximum accuracy of 99.10%, showing robustness to variations in writing[21].

To identify incomplete characters a partial character recognition[PCR] method using geometric shapes was proposed by Kulkarni S.A. Multiple classifier such as Decision tree, SVM , Naive Bayes were used for evaluation[22].

The system developed by them achieved a correct recognition rate(CRR) of 94.92% for complete characters and 97.68% for partial characters[23].

The literature review done highlights the steady evolution of research that has been done for character recognition of MODI lipi. Various techniques that have been used so far range from traditional feature based technique to modern deep learning and hybrid models, with CNN's giving the highest recognition accuracy consistently.

Table 2. Tabular representation of various Feature Extraction methods to recognize MODI Script

Sr. No	Author	Research year	Feature Extraction / Other Methodology	Classifier	Dataset	Accuracy / Remark
1	Lekha Gadpade, Aruna Chmatkar[1]	2025	Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Naive Bayes	Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Naive Bayes	-	Reviewed and compared feature extractors and classifiers for MODI script. Shows SVM is the best method amongst in traditional methods
2	Varpe Sakhare S[14]	K, 2023	Convolutional Network	Neural	CNN, KNN, Deep Learning	99.78
3	Altaf Ramjon, et.al.[33]	2023	Convolutional Network	Neural	Convolutional Neural Network	98.7
4	Vishal Pawar, et.al[7]	2022	Convolutional Network	Neural	Convolutional Neural Network	91.62

5	Joseph et.al.[12]	S., 2021	Wavelet based Recognition	Transform-Character	Decision Classifier- Daubechies, Haar, Symlet Wavelet	Tree 4600 characters(32 training, 1380(testing)	MODI 91.75
6	Joseph et.al.[13]	S., 2021	CNN- based Recognition	Character	CNN- Augmentation(On-the-Fly, Offline)	-	99.78(on-the-fly), 99.47(Offline).
7	Joseph et.al.[19]	S., 2021	CNN Auto based Recognition	encoder-Character	KNN,SVM	-	KNN- 99.4, SVM-99.3
08	Tamhankar P.A.,et.al.[16]	2021	CNN- based Recognition	Character	CNN with ReLU and Softmax	40,000	65
09	Mahajan et.al.[17]	2021	CNN- based Recognition	Character	CNN- Alex-Net	58 Characters-100 variations per characters	89.72
10	Chandure et.al[9]	S., 2021	Deep CNN with Pre-trained Net	(DCCN) Alex-Net	SVM(with Features from CNN Layers)	-	92.32
11	Shah et.al.[18]	R., 2021	Deep Neural Network for MODI OCR		Open NMT with Attention Mechanism	303571 synthetically generated MODI line images	99.97
12	Joseph et.al.[20]	S., 2021	Distance based Recognition	Classifier-Character	Euclidian, Manhattan Distance Classifiers	-	Euclidian-99.28 Manhattan-94
13	Joseph et.al.[15]	S., 2020	CNN Auto based Recognition	encoder-Character	CNN Auto encoder	4600 MODI Characters	99.3
14	Tamhankar P.A.,et.al[21].	2020	Character Segmentation and Recognition		Vertical Projection Profile (VPP)	-	67
15	Kulkarni S.A., et al.[23]	2021	Partial Recognition (PCR)	Character	Decision Tree, k-NN, LDA, QDA, SVM	-	97.68
16	Maurya R.K., et.al[26]	2018	Hybrid for Recognition	Feature Space Character	Fuzzy Logic Classification Affine Moment Invariants (AMIs)	-	91.20% (avg.), 99.10% (best)
17	Ajmire,P.E., et.al.[31]	2010	Basic structural features		Statical classifiers	Marathi vowels	Earlier stage work for Marathi vowels
18	Basekar, N., et.al.[30]	D. 2012	structural extraction	features	Rule-Based	MODI vowels	Discussed specialized recognition of vowels.
19	Kulkarni,	2014	Hu moments,	Zernike	Statistical Classifiers	-	Robust recognition

	S.A., et.al.[10]		moments, zoning				performance.
20	Deshmukh M., et.al.	2021	MODI Segmentation	Character Background	Pixel - Density Analysis		Proposed method for efficient character segmentation in MODI script.
21	Solanki B., et.al.[25]	2021	Image Enhancement and Binarization	Otsu Thresholding	-		Improved image binarization of MODI vowels using Otsu method.
22	Shekhar Chatterji[22]	2018	MODI Script Design	Font Unicode Font	-		Achieved high accuracy in recognizing handwritten MODI script.
23	Patil P.A., et.al.[27]	2016	Feature Extraction for MODI OCR	Fuzzy Logic Affine - Moment Invariants (AMIs)			Developed a Unicode font for MODI script for educational and archival purposes.

The Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 are the bar graphs for the accuracy rate according to different Authors as well as different techniques used by the authors

Fig 3. Comparative Accuracy by Research Studies

Fig 4. Method - Specific Accuracy Analysis

4. Conclusion

The MODI script being the primary writing system for the Marathi language until the 1950s has historic significance. Character identification of this script is difficult because of its complicated structure. To improve the accuracy of character identification in the MODI script, complex approaches must be implemented at each level of the process. This research examines and analyses the various existing "character recognition systems" for the MODI script. MODI Lipi has been successfully recognized using a variety of approaches, including OCR, Neural Networks, HMMs, SVMs, and CNNs. The method applied is chosen based on the application's requirements and the amount of training data available. The degree of efficiency varies depending on the method being used. A comparative study

of the methods that have been used to recognize the MODI script has shown that CNN and WT-SVD are the most effective, with CNN giving a maximum accuracy up to of 99.78%, and WT-SVD (Wavelet Transform-Singular Value Decomposition) of 99.56%

References

- [1] L. Gadpade and A. Chamatkar, "MODI Lipi character recognition using traditional machine learning algorithms," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Trends Technol.*, ICAMT25, pp. 199–202, 2025, ISSN: 2347-8578
- [2] C. Chandankhede and R. Sachdeo, "Offline MODI script character recognition using deep learning techniques," *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, vol. 82, no. 14, pp. 21045–21056, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-14476-0.
- [3] M. Deshmukh, M. Patil, and S. Kohle, "A divide-and-conquer based algorithm to detect and correct skew angle in historical handwritten MODI Lipi documents," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Appl.*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 47–63, 2017.
- [4] S. Chandure and V. Inamdar, "Offline handwritten MODI character recognition using GoogLeNet and AlexNet," in *Proc. 13th Int. Conf. Comput. Modeling Simulation*, pp. 1–6, 2021, doi: 10.1145/3474963.3474974.
- [5] S. Jadhav and V. Inamdar, "Invariant handwritten MODI character recognition using CNN and HOG," *Pattern Recognit. Image Anal.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 402–418, 2022, doi: 10.1134/S1054661822020109.
- [6] S. Joseph, A. Datta, O. Anto, S. Philip, and J. George, "OCR framework for MODI scripts using data augmentation and CNN," in *Data Science and Security*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 201–209, doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-5309-7_21.
- [7] V. Pawar, D. Wadkar, S. Kashid, P. Prakare, V. More, and A. Babar, "MODI Lipi handwritten character recognition using CNN and data augmentation," *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1880–1884, 2022.
- [8] S. Das, K. Wankhede, and A. Rituraj, "A review on MODI handwritten character recognition," *Int. Res. J. Modernization Eng. Technol. Sci.*, no. 11, pp. 1267–1274, 2022.
- [9] S. Chandure and V. Inamdar, "Handwritten MODI character recognition using transfer learning and discriminant feature analysis," *IETE J. Res.*, pp. 1–11, 2021, doi: 10.1080/03772063.2021.1902867.
- [10] S. A. Kulkarni, P. L. Borde, R. R. Manza, and P. L. Yannawar, "Offline handwritten MODI character recognition using Hu and Zernike moments," *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1406.6140, 2014.
- [11] R. Sachdeva, "Comparative analysis of zoning and distance profile features for handwritten Devanagari recognition," *Webology*, 2021.
- [12] S. Joseph and J. George, "Efficient handwritten MODI character recognition using wavelet transform and SVD," in *Data Science and Security*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 227–233, doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-5309-7_24.
- [13] S. Joseph and J. George, "Data augmentation for handwritten MODI character recognition using deep learning," in *ICT for Intelligent Systems*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 515–522, doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-7062-9_51.
- [14] K. Varpe and S. Sakhare, "Review of character recognition techniques for MODI script," *Indian J. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 16, no. 26, pp. 1935–1946, 2023.
- [15] S. Joseph and J. George, "Handwritten MODI character recognition using CNN feature extraction and SVM classifier," in *Proc. IEEE 5th Int. Conf. Signal Image Process.*, pp. 1–6, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICSIP49896.2020.9339435.
- [16] P. A. Tamhankar, K. D. Masalkar, and S. R. Kolhe, "Offline handwritten MODI document recognition using deep CNN," in *Commun. Comput. Inf. Sci.*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 478–487.
- [17] K. N. Mahajan and N. Tajne, "Ancient Indian handwritten MODI script recognition using deep learning," 2021.
- [18] R. Shah, M. K. Gupta, and A. Kumar, "Line-level MODI OCR using attention-based encoder–decoder architecture," in *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Image Inf. Process.*, pp. 273–278, 2021.
- [19] S. Joseph and J. George, "Convolutional autoencoder-based feature extraction for MODI script recognition," in *Data Science and Security*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 142–149.
- [20] S. Joseph and J. George, "Feature extraction and classification techniques for MODI script recognition," *Pertanika J. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 1649–1669, 2019.
- [21] P. A. Tamhankar, K. D. Masalkar, and S. R. Kolhe, "Character segmentation of handwritten MODI documents," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 171, pp. 179–187, 2020.
- [22] S. Chatterjee, "Designing a digital font for MODI script," *Ergonomics Int. J.*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2018.
- [23] S. A. Kulkarni and P. L. Yannawar, "Recognition of partial handwritten MODI characters using zoning," in *Commun. Comput. Inf. Sci.*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 407–430.
- [24] M. S. Deshmukh and S. R. Kolhe, "Hybrid segmentation of cursive handwritten historical MODI documents," *SSRN Electron. J.*, 2019.

- [25] B. Solanki and M. Ingle, "Performance evaluation of thresholding techniques on MODI script," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Adv. Comput. Telecommun.*, pp. 1–6, 2018.
- [27] P. A. Patil, "Character recognition system for MODI script," *Int. J. Comput. Eng. Res.*, 2016.
- [28] S. L. Chandure and V. Inamdar, "Performance analysis of handwritten Devanagari and MODI recognition systems," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Analytics Security Trends*, pp. 513–516, 2016.
- [29] A. K. Sadanand, K. Wankhede, A. Rituraj, and P. L. Yannawar, "Offline MODI character recognition using complex moments," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 58, pp. 516–523, 2015.
- [30] D. N. Besekar, "Special approach for handwritten MODI vowel recognition," *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, pp. 48–52, 2012.
- [26] R. K. Maurya and S. R. Maurya, "Recognition of medieval MODI script using hybrid feature space," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 136–142, 2018.
- [31] P. E. Ajmire and S. E. Warkhede, "Handwritten Marathi vowel recognition," 2010.
- [32] C. Chandankhede, "Handwritten MODI Lipi Barakhadi dataset," *IEEE Dataport*, 2023, doi: 10.21227/x24n-wm25.
- [33] Ramjon, Altaf & Bwatiramba, Asherl & Venkataraman, Sivakumar. (2023). :Handwritten Character Recognition Using Deep Learning (Convolutional Neural Network)". *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems. Volume 14. 2023. 10.7176/CEIS/14-1-05.*